

MODULE RE-DESIGN FOR HOLISTIC APPROACH TO TEACHING CHEMICAL PROCESS SAFETY

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Abstract

This paper shares the experience from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) from Singapore Polytechnic (SP) in revamping its Year 3 core module entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*. The module is often perceived by students to be dry and boring, and assessments are often a test of memory work on factual information. The traditional approach to teaching chemical process safety is via "Learning from Accidents" where case studies are used for classroom discussion during which useful lessons are drawn through analysis of root causes of the world's major industrial incidents involving chemical plants. The availability of the Internet and general proliferation of mobile devices made this traditional approach ineffective as students can readily go to Google and obtain model answers to questions posed in these case studies. Through a self-evaluation process based on the 12 Standards contained in the CDIO Framework (<http://www.cdio.org>), we came up with an innovative framework to teaching the module, based on application of risk management strategies to the entire lifecycle of a given chemical plant, where appropriate safety measures can be implemented to address the chemical and process hazards present. We firstly summarize the teaching of chemical process safety in the DCHE curriculum, identifying the shortcomings of the current teaching approach. Secondly, we outline the work done to re-design the module, justifying the retention of the use of case studies as the pedagogy of choice, but modified the way these cases are used in the "Learning from Accidents" approach. We then share the learning outcomes of the revised module, and explain how we teach chemical process safety in the new approach. This involves scaffolding students' thinking in relation to the lessons learned from the Bhopal Gas Tragedy, other selected cases, and one that we designed using dynamic simulation. Lastly, we share some learning points and plans to move forward.

Keywords: *chemical engineering, chemical process safety, CDIO, module re-design, case study*

Introduction

Chemical and process safety is an important component in chemical engineering education. It is a requirement from professional bodies that accredit chemical engineering programs such as the Institution of Chemical Engineering (IChemE), UK. However, the teaching of safety to chemical engineering students needs improvement (Louvar & Hendershot, 2003). The subject is taught in essentially all chemical engineering programs. A major challenge in the teaching of chemical process safety is that students often cannot readily identify with the safety issues as they lacked the relevant real-world experiences in the chemical processing industries. Chemical process safety is unlike other core chemical engineering subjects such as fluid mechanics, heat and mass transfer, separation processes and reaction kinetics which has strong design components requiring significant theoretical underpinning knowledge and involved mathematical calculations using various formulas. Issues in chemical process safety, as well as the proposed solution, on the other hand, are often sounded common sense in hindsight, and laden with many factual information. Students typically found the traditional lectures boring and hence only engage in surface learning. Teaching of HAZOP (hazard and operability) is particularly troublesome, as students' lack of actual working experience in chemical plant means that they are not able to effectively consider plausible undesirable consequences resulting from a process plant upset (Cheah, 2010).

The challenge further deepens as today's chemical plants become more integrated, where operational upset in one process unit can have consequences elsewhere in another different process unit. The level of risk has increased in the chemical processing industries (Kidam, et al, 2013). There must be greater integration of chemical process safety with other core subjects in chemical engineering as well as research programs (Mann, et al, 1999). There are three ways of incorporating chemical process safety into the chemical engineering curriculum: (1) a course or courses devoted to process safety, (2) integration of chemical process safety into existing courses and (3) a combination of the two approaches. Pintar (1999) gave detailed discussions on the relative merits of each approaches.

Chemical Process Safety in DCHE Curriculum

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) is a 3-year program, offered in Singapore Polytechnic (SP). The diploma is accredited by the IChemE, UK; which specifically requires that safety topics be adequately integrated in key categories of the curriculum, namely: (a) core chemical engineering, (b) engineering practice, and (c) design and design practice. In DCHE, we used the third approach in the teaching of chemical process safety, i.e. with a dedicated module as well as integration into other core modules throughout the diploma's three year curriculum. More specifically, we employ the following strategies:

- A 60-hour Year 3 core module entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* that is compulsory for all 120 students. Based on fully in-course assessment, this module has no final examinations. It also does not have any practical activities in the laboratories. This module covers many safety topics, ranging from hazard identification, risk assessment, plant safety systems, chemical safety data sheets, fire and explosions, safe work practices, etc; often in isolation from each other. We also spent a small portion of curriculum hours on a teaching approach widely known as "Learning from Accidents" in the safety literature; where case studies that present students with the real accidents involving major chemical plants that have occurred that have resulted in either death, injury or at least property loss, are used for classroom discussion. Examples of such case studies are the Bhopal Gas Leak Disaster, Flixborough Explosion, and Piper Alpha Accident. The objective is to draw out useful lessons through analysis of the root causes of these accidents that can be used to prevent future accidents.
- Integration of safety into all laboratory activities that support the learning of key chemical engineering concepts and principles in core modules: there is an explicit section on hazard identification and safety precautions, and where students are assessed on the ability to identify hidden hazards, and link the selection of appropriate personal protective equipment to these hazards. Students are assessed on their ability to do this, before they are permitted to continue with the laboratory activities. Students are also evaluated for their safety consciousness throughout the entire duration of the activities, as well as proper house-keeping at the conclusion of each activity
- Integration of safe practices into students' Final Year Projects (FYPs). All students are required to attend a risk assessment workshop. The students then conduct a risk assessment on the FYP that they plan to work on, together with their project supervisors and technical support officers from the laboratory where their FYP is located.

This paper focus on the first approach, which had several shortcomings in the way it is currently taught; making it ripe for a complete revamp. The various safety topics in the module are not explicitly connected

to the case studies used in "Learning from Accidents"; and all assessments in the module are pretty much conducted topic-by-topic, with hardly any in-depth linkage back to the case studies. Assessments for this module also tend to test mostly memory work, rather than critical analysis. Besides HAZOP, there is also lack of integration with other Year 3 core modules such as *Chemical Reaction Engineering* and *Plant Design, Economics and Sustainable Development*. In the former students learnt about chemical reaction kinetics and the application in designing chemical reactors, and are also required to operate simple reactors in the laboratory; but had no coverage on chemical reaction runaway, one of the most common hazards encountered in the operation of chemical reactors. In the later, students are required to complete a design of a chemical process plant using computer modelling, and prepare the necessary process piping and instrumentation diagram. Students are expected to make the connections between these modules for themselves; and often this do not happen.

The opportunity to revamp the *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* module arises from the rationalization of the course structure, where the module was shifted from Year 2 to Year 3 for its "integrative" nature (Cheah and Koh, 2013). This move is very appropriate, as it allows the use of safety topics to integrate the core modules taught in the first two years of study. It also challenge us to design learning tasks that can engage students in critical and creative thinking in relation to chemical process safety, given their lack of practical real-world experience, and the immense amount of background information that is needed to provide the right context to develop deep learning.

Methodology

For the re-designed module, we decided to retain the use of case studies as the pedagogy of choice and to design the entire module around case studies, with enhanced focus using the "Learning from Accidents" approach. Shallcross (2013) argued that case studies had been identified by many educators as an effective method to teach chemical process safety. He also reported on an alternative approach in which groups of students prepare presentations for delivery to the class, each group looking at a different case study. This approach, it is claimed, not only allows students to learn more deeply about one specific case study but it also helps to improve their communication skills. Saleh and Pendley (2012) presented an example whereby the entire subject on chemical engineering safety relies in part on the use of case studies. In all these instances, the most common method of using case studies in promoting student learning is to present selected cases in lectures taking time to highlight key points and the chain of events that led to the disasters. The key learning points are then presented. However, we felt that such approach is not effective, because these 'high-profile' incidents are already very well documented, and students only need to go to Google to look for model answers. As noted by Pitt (2012): "The official 'lessons

learned' can be pasted in or even memorized for the exam but not applied elsewhere."

The innovation in our approach derives from the insight we gained when we carried out a self-evaluation of the current module based on the CDIO Standards. The details of our approach are covered elsewhere (Cheah and Lee, 2015) and in this paper we only focused on the key outcomes of this effort. Most importantly, we noted that a typical chemical plant can be viewed as a major chemical product or system that went through the same four processes of conceiving, designing, implementing and operating embodied in the CDIO Framework. Applying Standard 1 "CDIO as Context" to this module leads to the new approach to re-design the *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* based on hazard identification and risk management around the lifecycle of a chemical plant; as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Integrated Approach to Teaching Chemical Process Safety. (List of abbreviations: MOC = Management of Change, LOPA = Layers of Protection Analysis, HAZOP = Hazard & Operability, FTA = Fault Tree Analysis, SDS = Safety Data Sheet, SWP = Safe Work Practices, ISD = Inherently Safer Design)

It had been cautioned that despite the wealth of information from so many accident investigation reports, the transfer of such "Learning from Accidents" had not been satisfactory (Sinclair, 2013). We hope that using the framework in Figure 1, we can better prepare our students in their learning about chemical process safety and apply the lessons learnt in a more effective manner to contribute to accident prevention in the workplace.

The non-technical key features of Figure 1 relevant to this work are briefly explained. The top-most box

shows the types of hazards under consideration for chemical engineering, broadly classified as "chemical" and "process" hazards respectively. The middle section shows a typical plant lifecycle (adapted from CCPS, 2009). The large box at the bottom are the key topics relevant to loss prevention in the chemical process industries; broadly grouped as legal requirements, risk management strategies and risk management toolbox.

In this model, we specifically link risk management strategies such as inherently safer design (ISD) to the different phases of the chemical plant's lifecycle. Due to the myriad of techniques and methods available and the limited time for the module, our toolbox is confined to the tools and techniques most pertinent in the field of chemical engineering, in particular HAZOP and LOPA (layers of protection analysis), with special emphasis on Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) and Pressure Relief Systems. With the "Learning from Accidents" approach, we then select suitable case studies of major accidents and guide students through these case analysis by firstly identifying the stage of the plant's lifecycle, to identify which risk management principles had been violated, the hazards involved, followed by application of proper safety measures available from the toolbox. With this approach, we hope to encourage our students to think critically and creatively from first principles and not rely on following codes, standards and rules (Lee, 1999).

Another outcome of our module review worth noting is CDIO Standard 6 Engineering Workspaces. At first glance, it would appear that this standard is not applicable to the *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* module, since it does not have any practical components. In applying this standard in our module review, we extend the interpretation of workspaces beyond that of physical locations to include virtual environments such as those afforded by dynamic simulation (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Sample Dynamic Simulation Model showing part of the Amine Treating Unit (ATU) from EnVision

With this, we can scaffold students' learning to build up their understanding of typical chemical process operations, and how to respond to process upsets and

various equipment malfunctions. This involves getting them to think critically (e.g., analyzing, comparing and contrasting, making inferences and interpretations, evaluating) in completing various simulation exercises; which is not possible in the academic settings, and risky in an actual chemical plants. They are asked specific questions to cue these main types of thinking (e.g., what inferences and interpretations can be made from the data presented; what is the best option to solving this problem given the inferences and interpretation being made).

The last CDIO Standard of interest is Standard 8 Active Learning; as it challenges us to look for innovative ways to engage students in studying this module. We decided to adopt flipped learning (also used synonymously with flipped classroom) coupled with peer instruction. Our experience is beyond the scope of this paper and will be shared elsewhere at a later date.

Summary of Programme Implementation

The 60-hour module is completely revamped in terms of its learning outcomes, module contents, and mode of delivery and approaches to student engagement. It is delivered in blocks of 2-hour Lecture and 2-hour Tutorial, for a total of 4 hours per week (hpw), for a total of 15 weeks in a semester. Time required of students for flipped learning is not included in the total module hour. The re-designed module has the following learning outcomes representing higher-order applications:

1. Apply application of loss prevention principles to key stages of a process plant life cycle
2. Explain key terminologies of process hazards and risks
3. Apply layer of protection analysis on a process system
4. Apply hazard analysis techniques for qualitative (such as HAZOP) and quantitative (such as HAZAN) risk assessment
4. Apply fire and explosion prevention and protection principles to chemical design and operation
5. Apply safe work practices according to industrial standards and regulations
6. Examine the ethical and responsibility issues the responsibility and ethical issues in the management of process safety

We use the Bhopal Gas Tragedy as the "anchor" case to illustrate how application of various risk management strategies can be used to avoid the use of dangerous chemical, or to properly assess the risk involve, or to provide more reliable safeguards, etc; as shown in Table 1.

The time freed up with flipped learning allows us to introduce more cases that were originally possible with the earlier curriculum. Where appropriate, we supplement the classroom activities with other case studies, mostly available from the U.S. Chemical Safety and Investigation Board (CSB); but also from YouTube videos and animations from reputable sources such as SIS vendors. We also develop our own case study based

on the Amine Treating Unit (ATU) dynamic simulation model available from EnVision Systems. The learning tasks more or less parallel that of the Bhopal case and are used during tutorials (as well as parts of the module in-course assessments) to evaluate how well students are able to apply these concepts. Using dynamic simulation, students can learn how the relevant safety system in the plant is activated when a hazardous condition is detected, and how the hazard is contained.

Table 1. Learning from Accidents using Bhopal Case

Wk	Safety Topic	Bhopal Case
1	Plant lifecycle Risk Manage	Background information
2	Process Chemistry: Inherently safer synthesis	Alternative pathway that avoids using the lethal chemical MIC
3	LOPA: Safety Instrumented System	Insufficient redundancy, inadequate design
4	LOPA: Pressure Relief System	Relief scenarios, wrong sizing of relief valve
5	Risk Matrix, Swiss Cheese	History of past accidents, multiple failures
6	Hazard Analysis: HAZOP	Application to MIC Storage Tank
12	Fault Tree Analysis	Causes of MIC leakage, lack of training
15	Safe Work Practices	Positive isolation, Safety Data Sheet for MIC
17	Summary	Ethics re-visited
<u>Note:</u> No lesson for Mid-semester test week (Week 8), and term break (Weeks 9-11).		

As shown in Table 1, we frequently re-visit the Bhopal case, as the weeks progressed when a new topic is covered. For example, on week 4, students learnt about pressure relief systems (PRS) and they are asked to evaluate various scenarios where an equipment over-pressure may occur. In another example, where students learned about various process disturbances and equipment malfunctions in the ATU in week 5, then revisited the Bhopal accident on week 6, to reinforce and extend their learning through linking how such an incident could have been prevented had a proper HAZOP is conducted. The students are also required to apply HAZOP to other cases, such as the BP Texas Refinery Gas Explosion.

We map out the entire 15-week lesson plan for the module, carefully converting factual information of the cases and theories on the safety topics into online versions for flipped learning. A sample 3-week lesson plan is shown in Table 2.

During later lessons, especially after Week 12, by which we had sufficiently covered various aspects of chemical process safety using Bhopal, ATU and other cases in particular the BP Texas Refinery Gas Explosion, we started introducing additional cases and at appropriate situations, assess students on their ability to relate current case with previous cases covered so as

to apply lessons learnt from previous cases to the case at hand. We conclude the module with an analysis of the ethical issues embedded in the Bhopal case, and then comparing and contrasting these with a case study based on the video "Incident at Morales"

Table 2 Sample Lesson Plan for Weeks 2-4

	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
Learning Outcomes	Understand the Application and Management of Loss Prevention in Chemical Plants	Understand Basic Components in Safety Management	Understand Basic Components in Safety Management
Flipped Learning Topics	Principles of Loss Prevention Inherently safer process + video Management of change Bhopal video, with specific attention of above concepts	Layer of Protection Analysis (LOPA) Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) See also link to web page ATU: Process Description	Pressure Relief Systems (PRS), see also link to web page CSB Video: BP Texas refinery explosion Visit W318 Gas Absorption Pilot Plant & line trace
Classroom Activities (2 hpw)	Clarify Bhopal Case Use Bhopal Case and discuss concepts Loss Prevention Principles & Inherently Safer Design, Management of Change	LOPA and SIS as examples of Concepts of Loss Prevention LOPA and SIS in Bhopal Case Readiness Check on ATU Process Description (Q&A)	Analysis of scenarios and sizing of relief valve in Bhopal – not sized for scenario of runaway reaction; sized for vapour only, not V-L flow CSB Video: BP Texas refinery explosion
Tutorial Activities (2 hpw)	Intro (pre-ATU) to Gas treating: ISD in solvent selection Apply inherent safety concepts to Piper Alpha	Worked examples on LOPA/SIS from existing materials ATU Case Study: Analyze LOPA, alarms, SIS	Analysis of W318 Gas Absorption Pilot Plant relief scenarios ATU Case Study: Relief scenarios (including worst-case of vapour blow-through)

As for the design of learning tasks, we strive to attain curriculum alignment (Biggs, 2003) for all the activities introduced in the module. In particular, we are looking for evidence whereby students can identify stages in the chemical process plant whereby appropriate risk management strategies can be applied, using the safety measures appropriate for the hazard identified. This is illustrated with three examples below.

Example 1: BP Texas Refinery Explosion

In this activity, which is carried out in Week 4, the students are required to watch the CSB Video as part of flipped learning. They had learnt about elements of LOPA earlier in Week 3 when analyzing the Bhopal case. Students then had to generate and evaluate possible ways to improve the safety in the BP plant using suitable elements of LOPA.

Example 2: Fire & Explosion at Formosa Plastics

In this activity, which is carried out in Week 13, the CSB Video is watched and analyzed in class, where students identify issues highlighted and organize them under different stages of the plant's lifecycle covered in Week 1. Students are expected to be able to retrieve the proper Safety Data Sheets relevant to this case, having learnt about usage of Safety Data Sheets in Bhopal in earlier lessons. They also need to implement a proper containment measure to mitigate the situation in the plant which is missing in the original design.

Example 3: Learning from Accidents - Valero

In this activity, which is carried out in Week 14, the lecturer play the CSB Video "Fire from Ice – Valero LPG Explosion" in class, and students are asked to answer a series of questions at appropriate points when the video is paused. The questions are listed below.

- Q1. What is the financial loss of the incident?
- Q2. In terms of separation processes, what unit operation is the Propane Deasphalting Unit?
- Q3. What are the properties of propane relevant to this situation?
- Q4. What type of fire is this known as? How is it different from that in Feyzin?
- Q5. What would be the inherently safer way to deal with the problem of the dead leg?
- Q6. Name an example of freeze-protection that can be used.
- Q7. What can you recall from the Formosa fire example in handling the fuel source?
- Q8. What is fireproofing and why is it useful?
- Q9. Back to lesson on inherently safer design – what is the lesson learnt here?
- Q10. Feyzin re-visited – what are the lessons learnt that can be applied to this case?

Students are expected to use the knowledge gained from earlier lessons, where inherently safer design, use of Safety Data Sheets, LOPA, etc; are employed, past accidents (namely Formosa Plastics and Feyzin), in the detailed analysis of this case.

We initially thought that the Bhopal Gas Tragedy, given the high profile attention that it continues to attract even to this day, and the apparent abundance of information available on the Internet, will be a relatively straight-forward case that we can adopt for our module re-design work. We soon realized that there were limited technical details in all the available resources that match the learning outcomes we strive to achieve. As a result, we wrote our own background information pack for Bhopal, and reference it throughout the weeks as we explore different safety topics as shown in Table 1. Adapting other past accidents into the module for discussions are more straight-forward. The challenge

here is in going through the vast CSB Database to select the case best meet the desired learning outcomes.

The challenge in "Learning from Accidents" is to understand how one can apply the lessons to one's own processes, even though the process or technology used is different from that involved in another accident from which the lessons are derived from (Hendershot, 2014). The revamp effort is only part of the holistic approach to teaching of chemical process safety. Although it is the biggest part, it is not complete without the other 2 approaches mentioned earlier: that of learning about safety via laboratories activities that simulate real-world practice, and final year projects. As can be seen from Figure 1, the module *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* focused on the technical aspects of safety management in the chemical process industries. To achieve a truly holistic approach, we will also need to leverage on the laboratory activities to develop other aspects on safety management such as safety culture, which is important element in reducing future re-occurrence of accidents (Capelle, 2013).

Conclusions

As noted by Knegtering & Pasma (2009), in response to the complexity of today's chemical plants, there is a need for a new approach to learn from past incidents. We believe the new approach presented in this paper will better engage students in learning about chemical process safety from past accidents. The redesigned *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* module was introduced to Year 3 students for the first time in April 2015. At the time of this writing, the teaching of this module is still on-going. We planned to survey the students for their learning experience for this redesigned module, to identify areas where they faced challenges, and formulate action plans to address them as part of continual improvement.

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References

- Biggs, J. (1999). *Teaching for Quality Learning at University*, Buckingham, UK: SRHE and Open University Press
- Capelle, T.V. (2013). Why Is It so Difficult to Learn from Someone Else's Mistakes? *Chem. Eng. Transactions*, Vol. 31, pp.505-515
- CCPS (2009). *Inherently Safer Chemical Processes: A Life Cycle Approach*, 2nd Ed., Center for Chemical Process Safety, Hoboken NJ: John Wiley & Sons
- Cheah, S.M. (2010). Overcoming the Barriers to Learning HAZOP via the Use of Dynamic Simulation, *Proc of the 4th International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*; Sep 28-30; Kagoshima, Japan
- Cheah, S.M. and Koh, H.W. (2013). Curriculum Integration in Chemical Engineering using CDIO: General Approach, *Proceedings of the 7th International Symposium on Advances in Technology Education*, September 25-27, Nara, Japan
- Cheah, S.M. and Lee, H.B. (2015). Module Review and Redesign via Self-Evaluation using CDIO Standards, *Proceedings of the 11th International CDIO Conference*, June 8-10, Chengdu, Sichuan, China
- Hendershot, D.C. (2014). Learning from Experience Revisited, *J. of Chem. Health & Safety*, 21(3), pp.35
- Kidam, K., Ahmad, A., Hassan, O., & Hurme, M. (2013). Current Issues and Challenges of Loss Prevention in the Chemical Process Industry, *Proc of the 6th International Conference on Process Systems Engineering*, Jun 25-27; Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
- Knegtering, B., & Pasma, H.J. (2009). Safety of the Process Industries in the 21st Century: A Changing Need of Process Safety Management for a Changing Industry, *J. of Loss Prev. in the Proc. Ind.*, 22; pp.162-168
- Lee, J.F. (1999). Education of Undergraduate Engineers in Risk Concepts, *Health & Safety Executive*
- Louvar, J.F. & Hendershot, D.C. (2003). SACHE: 17 years of Promoting Teaching of Safety to Chemical Engineering Students, *J. of Chem. Health & Safety*, Sep/Oct Issue, pp.8-10
- Mannan, M.S., Akgerman, A., Anthony, R.G., Darby, R., Eubank, P.T., & Hall, K.R. (1999). Integrating Process Safety into ChE Education and Research, *Chem. Eng. Educ.*, Summer; pp.198-209
- Pintar, A.J., (1999). Teaching Chemical Process Safety: A Separate Course Versus Integration into Existing Courses, *ASCE Annual Conference Proceedings*, June; Charlotte, NC
- Pitt, M.J. (2012). Teaching Safety in Engineering, *4th International Symposium for Engineering Education*, The University of Sheffield, July 18-20; UK
- Saleh, J.H., & Pendley, C.C. (2012). From Learning from Accidents to Teaching about Accident Causation and Prevention, *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, 99, pp.105-113
- Shallcross, D.C. (2013). Safety Education through Case Study Presentations, *Ed. for Chem. Engrs*, 8, pp.e12-30
- Sinclair, S. (2013). Process Safety - Learning from the Past and Implementing for the Future, *CHEMECA* September 29 - October 2, Brisbane, Australia